

TOPOLOGICAL SUMMARY OF W4W1

The following questions, extracted from a failed Fulbright Scholar application (September 2020), were posed in and across Phase One: “Useless Beauty” (2019-2021) of the ongoing Works for Works (W4W) project. Drawing upon OOI-MTA experiments in artistic scholarship across that two-year trajectory, the preliminary answers (as below), which may also appear to some as paralogisms, suggest what is at stake in Phase Two: “No Rights” (2022-).

1.1 – IPR and Its Discontents

Given the contemporary transposition of immaterial labour to forms of spectral commodity, with a focus on monetizing the knowledge commons, what possible means of **restoring value to so-called useless works in the Arts and Humanities** might impact both academia and the art world, where, on the one hand, we have an increasingly intense metrics-driven culture conditioning and evaluating all research, and, on the other hand, we have an advanced form of Guy Debord’s integrated spectacle subsuming all artistic production, both a status for works that places author rights at risk of systematic conformity to the prevailing neo-utilitarian bias and/or hegemony of new forms of patrimonialism and platform culture?

Preliminary answer: Through production and dissemination either beyond or across academic and art-world auspices, the works-for-works model introduces dissonance and exposes biases. In doing so, it also opens up other options that may then be further tested.

1.12 – The Privatization and Digitization of the Knowledge Commons

With the mass digitization of cultural production advancing on two fronts, the for-profit and the not-for-profit, the author has been summarily caught in the crosshairs, reduced to working for careerist motives

and/or servicing the aspirations of the vectoral class. What might permit the author to **escape both forms of marginalization and co-optation** and return to works that have no relation to either system of commodification of works?

Preliminary answer: Escape occurs through works, not in advance by negating options. Other options appear, some within the existing exigencies of systems as exception. This occurs most often when the system engaged is undergoing a shift and/or deconstruction from within (versus from without).

1.13 – Platform Cultures and Moral Rights of Authors

The advance of globalization of the knowledge commons is premised on making the knowledge commons “available” and “open” to all. What are the true motives for this agenda and what do capitalist and not-for-profit institutional prerogatives have in common? What is the **position of the artist-scholar** in the dialectical machinery of such a political economy? What is “artistic research,” as opposed to artistic scholarship, and why is contemporary artistic research said to service platform economy and art-world spectacle?

Preliminary answer: The artist-scholar is foremost, under present conditions, a nomad and rebel. This takes the form of precarity – but with precarity also operating as voluntary exile.

1.14 – Forms of Artistic Scholarship Present and Past

Setting aside the current penchant for practice-based artistic research, as espoused by art schools around the world, and leading to a peculiar “sameness” to works to be found in all such schools, plus a sameness that may be found in the art-industrial establishment worldwide (biennales, residencies, *kunsthallen*, etc.), **what types of artistic scholarship might be developed, or re-developed, toward freeing the artist-scholar from both careerist agendas, as enforced by academia and the art world, and commodification of works** toward mere survival in an increasingly oversaturated mediatized cultural commons?

Preliminary answer: The primary exit strategy is through a collectivist ethos (and telos) for works. “For works” also indicates that the collectivist ethos is based on the necessity of honoring the inborne agency of works, such that they also remain free of overt or banal attempts to leverage them by members of the collective as symbolic capital thus serving to reinsert them into the very games exposed as given to corrupting and/or co-opting works.

1.2 – Transitional States for Works

If precarity is now the standard operating position for artists and scholars, and for artist-scholars, **what are the possible or extant transitional states** that will lead to works that do not fall prey to the twin exigencies of academic careerism and art-world opportunism?

Preliminary answer: The primary modus vivendi for artist-scholars is to enter into the existentialist paradoxes of non-proprietary works (often an alchemical “nigredo”) and observe what occurs. Given contemporary biases that may be said to counter works-based agency from without (e.g., the application of PC agendas and/or ideological posturing), the transitional state for works of an entirely useless tenor (“useless” being utilized in tension with what is otherwise defined as “useful” by prevailing standards and neo-utilitarianism), the transit through the existentialist paradoxes will tend to engage variations on the theme of authorial privilege versus collectivist ethos (and telos).

1.21 – Transmedia as Transitional State for Works

The emergence of time- and performance-based work as the new ultra-contemporary modality in which to pursue artistic research prompts numerous questions regarding the assimilation of performance, installation, and forms of post-cinema to art-world spectacle. What are the **cross-platform, transdisciplinary editing strategies** for such works that might also lead the artist and author to counter the hyper-

temporality of such works and the spectral commodification via “event” that serves to privilege such works?

Preliminary answer: Privileging works-based agency tends to produce works that may take any number of forms, although in terms of forms of artistic scholarship the prevailing modalities of academia and the art world may be utilized and/or customized to edition and disseminate “records” and “reports” on projects that otherwise remain within a circumscribed zone best described as “portfolio” or “archive.”

1.22 – Time- and Performance-based Works

If **time- and performance-based works** are the latest fashion statement in the art world and in art academies, are they forms of critical inquiry and how so? Is the present-day penchant for socio-cultural criticism in such works, or by way of such works, a subtle form of appropriation and neutralization of the artwork’s autonomy and formal agency or is such content a valid transitional state toward a new avant-garde for post-capitalist artworks? Additionally, why has the art-critical and art-curatorial establishment declared the modernist concept of an avant-garde elitist and/or a fiction?

Preliminary answer: Time- and performance-based works are not guilty in and of themselves as serving intellectual and artistic fashions. How they are used is what determines whether they escape the overt and/or subtle mechanisms of control exerted by academia and the art world. Thus, time- and performance-based works may be a part of, but not the overriding concern of new forms of avant-garde artistic scholarship. Moreover, the inherent or inborne radical agency of such works will negate any re-imposed socio-cultural “cut” or “bias” that might re-insinuate itself as new fashion statement. In observing and honoring the agency of the work, the artist-scholar will also refuse any accommodation with empty rhetorical gestures and/or posturing, except in the transitional states noted above, where such gesturalism may serve as vehicle for “report” or “record,” whereas the inborne agency of the work remains offstage in the “portfolio” or “archive,” to be replayed or remixed another time toward wholly new ends or no ends.

1.23 – The Transfer of Moral Rights to Works

What possible means exist, or might exist, for the **transfer of moral rights of authors to works**? Does this require a wholly new form of the editioning and archiving of works?

Preliminary answer: The transfer of moral rights to works is carried out through renunciation of authorial privilege. Renouncing rights includes preventing the theft or appropriation of such renounced rights by others. In this manner, the artist-scholar becomes steward versus author of works.

1.24 – Beyond the CC0 License and No Rights

How might the **final breach with IPR law** be made for works and through works in order to escape the last restriction – i.e., the fact that by IPR law moral rights may not be transferred and/or renounced, as is evident in the CC0 license? Additionally, why and to what end have moral rights been made subservient to statutory law and copyright?

Preliminary answer: Through the editioning and dissemination strategies of the works-for-works idiom, it is thereby the “idiomatic” in/for itself that provides the final breach. Multi-form, hybrid, and occasional stealth modalities permit elements of works to reside in various places, with the predictable outcome(s) minimized and the unexpected outcome(s) maximized. Works will, under this model, generally choose their own path beyond IPR law through where they are welcome and where they are not.

1.3 – Prior Art after IPR

What is the status of the concept of **Prior Art after IPR**? What possible future scenarios may be devised and/or theorized toward making Prior Art the basis for a futural class of works that have no relation to IPR? Is the Enlightenment-era concept of the “exceptional” status of the authored work not also the foundation

for many of the fictions underlying IPR and the contested or strained relation between moral rights and economic rights? How can this idea of “exception” be re-purposed?

Preliminary answer: Prior Art becomes the landscape of possibilities that opens up after intellectual property rights and abject careerism are abandoned. Examples of such landscapes also illustrate the recursive nature of the exit strategy (leaving to return), inclusive of negotiating current or incipient ecosystems in academia and the art world while denoting aporias and forms of dissension through analyses and reports on subjects such as: Art + Law; Performative Research; and Rites of Works.

1.31 – Works for Works

If “Works for Works” is to be defined as a class of works that has no relation to commodity status for works of artistic scholarship and no relation to IPR, have such works existed in the past, do they exist now, and how might they exist in the future? Does such a class of works re-constitute a past state for works or does it augur **a revolution in the very concept of works** and proprietary rights?

Preliminary answer: Works for Works, as idiomatic quest for new forms of artistic scholarship with no relation to Capital and its edicts, “builds” across works (as life-work for works) a “catalogue,” “portfolio,” or “archive,” which, in turn, specifies its own preferred means of expression (production and dissemination). This ecosystem is thus a proto-ecosystem for works that eventually come to reside in no one place and in no one time. Scriptorium and archive describe merely the surface of the extensivity of the model and its often-preposterous presentist time-sense.

1.32 – The Artist-Scholar

What is the “fugitive” **status of the artist-scholar past, present, and yet to come**? Where, how, and when did the separation of artist and scholar occur, or is it a false dichotomy?

Preliminary answer: The artist-scholar, as steward for works versus author, effectively abandons time as normally conceived. In the agency of works produced as “useless,” other times and other places emerge as expressive gestures and synchronistic time-senses. The works-for-works modality for artistic scholarship underscores what has always been at stake in the Arts and Humanities and which is increasingly imperiled by rote utilitarianism and the commodification of knowledge.